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Validation Procedure Of Mathematics Test Among Senior Secondary School Teachers In Sokoto State

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed teachers' competence in test construction and validation procedure of Mathematics test among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The objectives of this study was to Determine the teachers' competence in construction and standardization of Mathematics test based on educational qualification among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria. One research questions were raised to guide the study and three hypotheses were formulated and tested at $p \leq 0.05$ levels of significance. The study adopted a survey research design. The population of the study comprises of 1,787 senior secondary schools' Mathematics teachers. The population were obtained from one hundred and forty-five (145) senior secondary schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. A sample size of 132 Mathematics teachers was selected using cluster and simple random sampling technique. Data was collected using a questionnaire titled "Test Construction and Standardization of Mathematics Test Questionnaire" (TCSMTQ) adapted from Abdullahi (2019). The instrument was validated by three experts in measurement and evaluation, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The reliability of the items was determined using Cronbach's alpha reliability which yielded a coefficient of 0.75. Data collected were described and analyzed using statistical mean and standard deviation, percentage, independent sample t-test and Analysis of variance (ANOVA). All hypotheses were tested at $p \leq 0.05$ levels of significance. The results of the study showed that, significant difference exists in teachers' competence of test construction based on professional training ($p = 0.006 < 0.05$), no significant difference in teachers' competence in standardization of Mathematics test based on years of working experience ($p = 0.591 > 0.05$), and significant difference exists in teachers' competence in construction and standardization of Mathematics test based on educational qualification ($p = 0.001 < 0.05$) among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that teachers' competence of test construction based on professional training among senior secondary schools' teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria differ significantly. It was therefore recommended among others that the State' Ministry of Education should organize conferences, seminars, workshops, and given pre and in-service professional training programmes on test construction to non-professional teachers.

Keywords: teachers' competence, Mathematics test, secondary school

INTRODUCTION

The importance of teachers setting appropriate tests for their students is inarguable considering the value of test scores given by teachers (Inko-Tariah & Okon, 2019). Teachers should competent in teaching to give the best result consistent with best practice. That are the reasons why this study conducted to assess the teachers' knowledge in test construction and validation procedure to know how teachers are competent in developing test items. So the teachers can evaluate the lack of their teaching method,

materials, knowledge and attitude toward students (Rivai, Ridwan, Supriyati & Rahmawati, 2019). Others study demonstrated proficiency in assessment skills of the participants. Results showed teachers rating themselves higher than principals while principals rated themselves higher than supervisors. Generally, it was found that they all needed more training in test construction skill.

Rohaam, Taconis and Jochems (2012) claim that teacher knowledge on the subject plays an important role in influencing students' understanding. Therefore, it is suggested that a focus on developing knowledge on the subject will affect the level of confidence in teaching positively and can improve student achievement. Furthermore, Minor (2016), shows that high-quality teachers are confident and are better to answer student questions and focus on learning because they are supported by strong knowledge. They are more likely to provide deep and meaningful engagement with the subject. In order to assess both the success of students in learning process and the teacher in the teaching, assessment instruments must be used that include instruments made by the teacher which is high quality, reliable, and can be validated (Rivai et al, 2019).

The professional teacher is expected to possess certain competence both professional and personal (Nbina, 2012). Professional competences are both academic and pedagogical. Academic competencies are the teachers' knowledge of his subject. Thus, the quality of the objective test made by the teacher is influenced by the test construction knowledge. This is relevant with Agu et al (2013) findings which state that the quality of tests correlates with the teacher's ability to provide information needed to improve student performance. The ability to design test will lead to the accuracy in measuring learning outcomes and result in students' misunderstanding, and the effectiveness of the learning process. This means that cognitive ability, as an initial ability, is influenced by the character of a teacher's professional attitude, one of which is knowing how assessment can improve student learning achievement.

Dubem (2014) positioned that lecturers' competence in test construction is dependent on the personality and training rather than gender of the teacher as the skills in constructing good tests are acquired through training. There are basically nine teaching competencies identified, these are communication, availability, creativity, individual consideration, social awareness, feedback, professionalism, conscientiousness and problem solving (Catano & Harvey, 2014). Good teaching means teaching that conforms with the moral and rational principles of teaching practice, which invariably means that the content being taught meets the standards of the discipline in terms of adequacy and completeness. This is a developmental model about the generic abilities or factors of the educator that aim at identifying the broad ability of the teachers in the art of teaching and learning processes across grade levels.

The construction and validation of a Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) is a criterion referenced mastery test, which is aimed at determining the degree of mastery attained by primary five school students in mathematics tests (Margaret & Anthonia, 2017). Most Nigeria mathematics teachers employ Norm-referenced tests in assessing their students' performance. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) in her national policy on education described the secondary school as education children receive after primary education and before the tertiary stage. Mathematics is one of the senior secondary school subjects that require a systematic assessment to ascertain students' basic knowledge, skills, and understanding of the concepts. The test is then given to an equivalent group to the people the test is intended for trial testing, thereafter item analysis is by calculating the difficulty and discrimination indices of the items. Items are then selected based on the appropriate levels of these indices for norm and criterion-referenced tests (Inko-Tariah & Okon, 2019).

Test construction knowledge and teaching material attitude are one of the factor that can be a tool to evaluate the teacher and learning process. These tools can measure the learning goals so these should be precise and accurate as what teacher intends to measure and evaluate (Rivai et al, 2019). Adodo (2014) carried out an evaluative study of secondary school teachers' competence in evaluating students cognitive and psychomotor achievement in basic science and technology. The results revealed teachers' years of experience and qualifications did not significantly influence their competence in assessing their students while gender made a significant influence. The result is not surprising as only a teacher proficient in test construction procedures can construct tests that have the right psychometric properties.

The business of teaching and learning cannot be complete without a periodic examination of the learners to determine if set objectives are being achieved (Inko-Tariah & Okon, 2019). In the senior secondary schools of Sokoto central senatorial district, each teacher of Mathematics is expected to quantify how much the students have achieved from a course of instruction, this is done through the administration of tests by the teachers who may not have adequate knowledge of test construction procedures, hence most often one encounters question papers that lack the basic psychometric properties (validity, reliability, and usability). The most common tests used by teachers are teacher-made achievement tests as against standardized tests which have the psychometric properties established (Inko-Tariah & Okon, 2019). This help to determine the difficulty level, discriminatory index and check guessing (Osadebe, 2014). It is advisable to Mathematics teachers in Sokoto central senatorial district to double sample of test items because some may not survive item analysis.

Statement of the Problem

The present senior secondary school curricula demand that variety of assessments be carried out in the course of instruction to guide effective teaching. Sequel to this and the relatively scanty number of instruments for measuring students' achievement in Mathematics at secondary school level, teachers of the subject have continued to develop instruments for measuring students' achievement in the subject. Most teachers hurriedly copy questions from any past question paper to compose their summative achievement tests. As a result, teachers do not establish validity and reliability for such tests. Students are often assessed with poorly prepared achievement tests by their Mathematics teachers. The content areas of their tests in Mathematics are not spread out to cover the content of Mathematics curriculum.

Observations show that those teacher-developed testing instruments are generally of doubtful psychometric features since no serious attention might have been paid to their test construction and validation. For such instruments, either face validation or possibly construct validation was employed. Most of the Mathematics teachers in secondary schools do not seem to possess the competencies required in instrument development and validation. This means that for Mathematics teachers to use valid and reliable tests, experts in test construction have to develop them, otherwise the objective of our education system may not be achieved. Students are examined at every level of the senior secondary school with teachers made achievement tests until the end of the third year when they are finally assessed by WACE or NECO.

Consequently, such tests limit students' scope of reading and this leads to poor achievement in Mathematics. Students' good achievement in Mathematics at SSCE will depend to a large extent, coverage of the Mathematics curriculum as well as the use of valid and reliable Mathematics Achievement Tests to assess them. Therefore, it was as a result of the use of unreliable achievement test poorly designed by Mathematics teachers, and the need to provide a more valid and reliable Mathematics achievement test in senior secondary school, that the researcher conceived the idea to carry out a research on assessment of teachers' knowledge of test construction and validation procedures in Mathematics among senior secondary school in Sokoto central senatorial district of Sokoto state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study will be to:

1. Determine the teachers' knowledge of test construction and Validation procedures based on educational qualification in Mathematics among senior secondary school in Sokoto state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

This study will answer the following research questions:

To what extent are teachers' knowledgeable in test construction and Validation procedures based on educational qualification in Mathematics among senior secondary school in Sokoto state, Nigeria?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher adopted survey research design. Anikweze (2013) stated that surveys are applicable to the assessment of attitudes, achievements, feelings, opinions and perceptions of a large number of people at a particular time. Surveys are also used to measure any number of variables in a natural setting. It is the collection of information from a sample of individuals through their responses to questions. This design

was employed because the interest of the researcher is to examine and describe a certain variable in relation to a certain population. The survey has capacity to gather different set of data at the same time from the sample that were considered for the study to justify current condition and practice and make more plans for improving them. Therefore, this study adopted this design because it sought to obtain information from a representative sample of the population. The population of this study comprises of 1,787 senior secondary schools' Mathematics teachers of Sokoto State. The state has three senatorial districts (Sokoto East, Sokoto South and Sokoto Central senatorial zones) with four education zones which covered the state (Sokoto North, Sokoto Central, Sokoto East, and Sokoto West education zones) (See Appendix II). The population obtained from one hundred and forty-five (145) senior secondary schools from four education zones, and the target population of the study obtained from sixteen (16) senior secondary schools with a total number of two hundred and twenty-five (225) Mathematics teacher in Sokoto State. The choice of the population was because all mathematics teachers in the study area

Table 1: Population distribution according to local government area and schools

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S/No.	School	LGA	No of Teachers
1.	GDSS Alu Quarters Bado	Wamakko	17
2.	GDSS Birjingo	Goranya	15
3.	GDSS Illela	Illela	7
4.	GDSS Kurawa	Sabon Birni	16
5.	GDSS Maberu	Sokoto South	17
6.	GDSS Rabah	Rabah	13
7.	GDSS Romon Sarki	Tambuwal	15
8.	GDSS Sifawa	Bodinga	17
9.	GDSS Silame	Silame	14
10.	GDSS Tudun Yola	Sokoto North	19
11.	GDSS Turba	Isa	11
12.	GGASS Isa	Isa	9
13.	GGDSS Bodinga	Bodinga	13
14.	GGDSS Kware	Kware	15
15.	GGSS Sanyinna	Tambuwal	14
16.	GTC Binji	Binji	13
Total			225

Source: Sokoto State Ministry of Education Summary (2024)

The sampling technique used in the study was Cluster sampling technique in the selection of education zone, and simple random sampling technique was employed to select (4) schools from each education zone, making a total number of sixteen (16) schools. Simple random sampling was also used in selecting the participants where every participant has equal chance of being selected. The sample of 132 mathematics teachers were drawn using Research Advisors (2006) table for determining the sample size, and the sample of teachers in each school was selected proportionally according to the population of teachers in the schools selected for the study. The sample size distribution was presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Sample distribution of teachers by school and local government area

S/No.	School	LGA	Sample Size
1.	GDSS Alu Quarters Bado	Wamakko	10
2.	GDSS Birjingo	Goranya	9
3.	GDSS Illela	Illela	4
4.	GDSS Kurawa	Sabon Birni	9
5.	GDSS Maberu	Sokoto South	10
6.	GDSS Rabah	Rabah	8
7.	GDSS Romon Sarki	Tambuwal	9
8.	GDSS Sifawa	Bodinga	10
9.	GDSS Silame	Silame	8
10.	GDSS Tudun Yola	Sokoto North	11
11.	GDSS Turba	Isa	6
12.	GGASS Isa	Isa	5

13.	GGDSS Bodinga	Bodinga	8
14.	GGDSS Kware	Kware	9
15.	GGSS Sanyinna	Tambuwal	8
16.	GTC Binji	Binji	8
Total			132

The instrument for data collection were: Test Construction and Standardization of Mathematics Test Questionnaire (TCSMTQ) adapted from Abdullahi (2019). The questionnaire consists of sections A and B. Sections A consists the bio-data of the respondents as follows: name of school, gender, educational qualification and years of working experience, while section B consists 32 items that measured teachers' competence in construction and standardization of Mathematics test. The questionnaire was adopted the Likert format. Each item of the questionnaire was responded using a four point Likert Scale with the following responses: Always (A), Almost Always (AA), Sometimes (ST), and Not at All (NA). The responses were scored as (A) = 4, (AA) = 3, (ST) = 2, and (NA) = 1. Teachers was required to objectively express their opinions using the four point Likert Scale. The instrument (questionnaire) used for data collection for the study was already validated by its original author (Abdullahi, 2019). Despite the validation by the original author (Abdullahi, 2019), the researcher still consulted experts in Measurement and Evaluation from the department of Educational Psychology and Counselling, Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria for their consent about using the instrument (questionnaire). The corrections made by these experts were properly effected before the researcher used it as a valid instrument for the study. The reliability of the instrument (questionnaire) was already determined by its original author Abdullahi (2019). The author used Cronbach's alpha coefficient to test the internal consistency of the instrument (questionnaire). A coefficient of 0.82 indicated a high degree of internal consistency of the instrument (questionnaire). Also, the instrument (TCSMTQ) was tested for reliability using Cronbach's alpha method by the researcher. The result showed that the instrument was highly reliable with a reliability coefficient of 0.75. The researcher collected a letter of introduction titled "Students' Field Research" from the Department of Educational Psychology and Counselling, Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria to Sokoto State Ministry of Education. After approval from the Ministry of Education. The researcher visited all the sampled schools with approval letter for conducting research to collect data for the study. During the process of administration of the instrument, the researcher with the help of research assistant in each school distributed the questionnaire to the participants. The researcher explained the instructions verbally and allowed them to read the written instructions. The researcher also gave them room for asking questions for further clarification. The questionnaires were collected after filling by the participants to ensure 100% retrieve and finally, the instrument was subjected for further analysis. The data collected for this study were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Frequencies and percentages was used to describe the demographic variable of the participants. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. Independent sampled t-test was used to test hypothesis one, while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was also used to test hypotheses two and three. All hypotheses were tested at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

Research Question One: *How do teachers' competence in construction and standardization of Mathematics test are based on educational qualification among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of Mathematics teachers with respect to their level of qualifications on the competence in construction and standardization of Mathematics test.

Qualifications	N	Mean	SD
Diploma	10	50.60	5.232
NCE	59	54.69	6.109
HND	14	49.57	6.880
Degree	43	52.91	6.640
Higher Degree	6	56.50	5.010

Table 3 shows the mean scores of 50.60, 54.69, 49.57, 52.91 and 56.50 with a standard deviation of 5.232, 6.109, 6.880, 6.640 and 5.010 for teachers with Diploma, NCE, HND, Degree and Higher Degree qualifications. This table indicates that teachers with Higher Degree and NCE qualifications had a highest mean scores compared with the mean of Diploma, HND and Degree holders. It clearly showed that those mathematics teachers with different level of qualifications were competent in construction and standardization of Mathematics test among senior secondary school of Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The finding of this study showed that teachers with Higher Degree and NCE had a better mean scores compared with the mean score of Diploma, HND and Degree holders among senior secondary school teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Also, the result from hypothesis three indicated that teachers' competence in construction and standardization of Mathematics test differ significantly based on educational qualifications. Furthermore, Scheffe's test was performed and revealed that significant difference exists in the mean score of teachers' competence in construction and standardization of Mathematics test between NCE and HND, Higher Degree and HND qualifications. This finding is not in agreement with the result of Adeosun and Mogokwu (2024) found that there are no significant differences among the teachers' competency in test construction based on qualification. Waseka, Simatwa and Okwach (2016) showed the expected result that teachers with the Bachelor of Education qualification significantly influenced their students' performance, it also revealed the unexpected outcome with the discovery that teachers with the Master of Education or Diploma qualifications did not significantly influence the performance of their students. This study also contradicts with the findings of Inko-Tariah and Okon (2019) who found that lecturers' knowledge of test construction procedures did not differ significantly based on educational qualification. Ogbeide and Idusogie (nd) revealed that there is no significant difference in the teachers' qualifications and their level of competency in test construction. Camble and Hamman-Tukur (2017) revealed that a significant relationship between teacher qualification and their knowledge of test construction and validation procedures existed. Adodo (2014) found that the qualification of the teacher has no influence on construction of a table of specification which is also vital in the test construction process.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions were drawn from the findings of the study:

1. There exists a significant difference between Mathematics teachers with different levels of educational qualifications on the competence in construction and standardization of Mathematics test. Teachers with NCE and Higher Degree differ significantly with those holding HND. This shows that, teachers' with NCE and Higher were competence in construction and standardization of Mathematics test among senior secondary schools' teachers in Sokoto State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Unqualified Mathematics teachers such as HND holders should have additional qualifications with PGDE as teaching profession qualification and make use of the items of test construction and standardization of Mathematics test designed in the questionnaire as a guide in constructing a good quality test in Mathematics

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